

PERMEABILITY ENHANCEMENT WITH DIFFERENT GLASS FIBER QUASI-UD STRUCTURE ARRANGEMENTS FOR RTM-TP PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Three different types of a quasi-unidirectional fabric have been produced and studied in order to reach the objective of the enhanced longitudinal permeability. The overall goal of the project TAPAS is to use the optimised fabric in a RTM process adapted to high fluidity polyamide 6,6. Microstructure study is undertaken with Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and X-Ray Tomography (X-RT) images as well as image treatment by stereology. Permeability has been measured experimentally and estimated by an analytical model based on Kozeny-Carman relationship and by the inverse identification with the help of the Brinkman equation numerically solved by the Proper Generalized Decomposition method (PGD) and finite elements (FEM). Both models for the prediction of permeability seem to give comparable results, whereas experimental values of permeability are quite higher than model ones. The fact that both models give predictions with the help of 2D cut images should explain this discrepancy with experiments. Nevertheless, the same increasing trend in permeability for the three fabrics is observed both on experimental and analytical model values. Finally, an example of RTM-TP composite plate with PA6,6 and the most permeable fabric among the three, at a volume fraction of 54.2%, is given as a proof of concept.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in the automotive industry for thermoplastic composites has led to the creation of TAPAS (ThermoplASTic Process for Automotive composite Structure) project launched in 2012. It brings together French companies and public laboratories on the industrial feasibility of polyamide composites and its possible improvements.

To meet the industry requirements, TAPAS project focus on RTM process (Resin Transfer Molding) to develop glass fiber -reinforced high fluidity polyamide 6,6, at reduced processing time and with high mechanical properties. Therefore, two ways have been investigated: i. improvement of both fluidity and wetting properties of polyamide polymers; ii. increasing of permeability of glass fabrics. The latter one is discussed in this paper. In the project, targeted in-plane longitudinal permeability values of glass

fabrics should be around 10^{-9} m^2 for a minimum volume fiber content of 50%. Unidirectional or quasi-unidirectional fabrics only are considered.

In order to achieve this technological objective, a quasi-unidirectional fabric was tested in longitudinal permeability and its structure has been modified to produce further two new variants. By this way, the three lightly different structures can be physically tested and compared. Longitudinal saturated permeability experiments and analytical and numerical models as well as systematic microstructure studies are carried.

A composite plate with the more permeable tested fabric and PA6,6 is finally examined in the last section of this article.

In the remaining of the article, longitudinal permeability stands for the in-plane permeability along the UD warp tows.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Quasi-unidirectional fabric

Three quasi-unidirectional woven fabrics (called Ud1, Ud2 and Ud3) are all designed with 1200 tex glass yarns (warp) and 70 tex yarns (weft). Weft yarns are non-crimped and placed below and above warp yarns in a alternating way. Both main warp and weft yarns are maintained by crimped 34 tex warp yarns. These latter ones are called “spacers” as they maintain spaces between the main warp yarns. Ud2 and Ud3 differs from Ud1 by a double density of weft yarns, i.e. one every 5mm. Ud3 differs from Ud2 by an increase of spacer linear mass density (Table 1). Areal weight increases slightly from Ud1 to Ud3 as textile parameters evolves. Main warp yarns are constituted with fibers with an average radius of $9,0\mu\text{m}$.

Name	Measured Areal weight (g/m ²)	Main yarn (tex)	Warp spacer (tex)	Weft yarn (tex)	Distance between two weft yarns (mm)
Ud1	514,0				11
Ud2	542,9	1200	34	70	5
Ud3	594,3		136		5

Table 1: Structural and physical parameters values for the three quasi-unidirectional fabrics.

2.2 Microstructure examination

Composite plates at different volume fractions of fibers are elaborated by RTM using an epoxy resin. Samples are extracted by water cutting. Microstructures are then imaged with SEM (cross-sections images) and X-RT (3D images). Thickness of plates and samples is about 3.0mm.

2.3 Permeability measurements

Longitudinal permeability is measured experimentally along the warp direction in saturated regime for the three fabrics and at different volume fractions of fibers. Tests are conducted with silicon oil whose viscosity stands at 0.1 Pa.s at 25°C. Dimensions for all preforms are defined as 400mm, 90mm, 4.8mm for the length, width and thickness respectively.

2.4 Permeability models

A double-scale porosity model based on Kozeny-Carman relation is adapted here from [1]. “KC2S” model expresses geometrical permeability, K_{Geo} , as the sum of the permeabilities in macropores (spaces between yarns), K_M , and in micropores (spaces inside yarns between fibers), K_μ , weighed respectively with the surface fractions of the macropores, $A_A(P_M)$, and of the micropores, $A_A(P_\mu)$:

$$K_{Geo} = \frac{K_\mu A_A(P_\mu)[1 - A_A(P_M)] + K_M A_A(P_M)}{A_A(P)} \quad (1)$$

with the global surface fraction of porosity $A_A(P) = A_A(P_\mu)[1 - A_A(P_M)] + A_A(P_M)$. K_M and K_μ are given by Eq. 2.

$$K_M = \frac{c_M}{16} \overline{L(P_M)^2} A_A(P_M) \quad (2a)$$

$$K_\mu = \frac{c_\mu \pi^2}{64} r_f^2 \frac{A_A(P_\mu)^3}{(1 - A_A(P_\mu))^2} \quad (2b)$$

with c_M and c_μ , Kozeny constants for macropores and micropores respectively, $\overline{L(P_M)}$, mean free path inside macropores and r_f , mean fiber radius. $\overline{L(P_M)}$ is determined by averaging the mean free paths in the four principal directions (horizontal, vertical and both diagonals) on cross-section images of macropores (Fig. 1). Mean free paths in different directions are calculated by lineal granulometries.

Figure 1: a) SEM image of quasi-unidirectional fabric (Ud3); b) processed image after segmentation of warp, weft, warp “spacer” yarns regions, and pores regions.

A numerical methodology is developed based on the Brinkman equation [2] and its resolution by the Proper Generalized Decomposition method (PGD) [3] and finite elements (FEM). The employment of Brinkman equation is of particular interest because it allows taking into account the double-scale porosity structure of the quasi-unidirectional fabrics as follows:

$$\varphi \nabla \langle P_f \rangle^f = \mu \nabla^2 \langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle - \varphi \mu \mathbf{K}^{-1} \langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle \quad (3)$$

where $\langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle$ is the phase averaged fluid velocity, which is equal to the product of the intrinsic average fluid velocity $\langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle^f$ and porosity φ : $\langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle = \varphi \langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle^f$; μ is the fluid viscosity; $\langle P_f \rangle^f$ is the intrinsic average pressure; \mathbf{K} is the local permeability tensor of yarns characterizing the intra-yarn flow. Based on the obtained velocity and pressure field, the global permeability of fabrics is then identified using the Darcy’s law. An important point in the image-based macro-permeability evaluation is a correct attribution of different local permeability tensors to the corresponding three yarn regions that differ by their properties: warp, weft, and warp spacer yarns. A preliminary texture analysis, based on the evaluation of gray-level co-occurrence matrix and corresponding texture features, was performed on the SEM or X-RT images in order to distinguish regions of different fabric constituents.

3 MICROSTRUCTURE ANALYSIS

In order to obtain KS2C model values, macropores fraction area $A_A(P_M)$ is extracted from cross-section images of composites samples. Once $A_A(P_M)$ is determined, micropores fraction area $A_A(P_\mu)$ can be deduced. Fig.2 shows the evolution of both fraction areas as a function of the fabric and V_f . Among other things, $A_A(P_M)$ increases from Ud1 to Ud3 at constant V_f . It means that spaces between yarns that allow faster impregnation of the fabrics are more important in amount for Ud3. Therefore one expects an increase in permeability from Ud1 to Ud3.

Figure 2: Macropores and micropores fraction areas as a function of V_f for the three fabrics.

Fig.3 presents two 3D images obtained from X-RT with 7 plies of Ud2 and 6 plies of Ud3 and filtered in order to highlight macropores structure. Main warp yarns are the same in both samples but porosity is higher in the second image with larger white zones. It can also be seen on right hand side of both images the crimping “shadow” of the spacer yarns. This effect is larger in Ud3 than Ud2 because spacer yarn tex is four times higher in Ud3 than Ud2.

Figure 3: Macropores 3D images for Ud2 and Ud3 preforms.

4 PERMEABILITY COMPARISON

4.1 Permeability results

Experimental permeability is measured at different volume fractions of fibers between 40% and 63%. KC2S model is calculated at four different V_f and one point on Fig. 4 correspond to one cross-section image for which all parameters in Eq. 1 are calculated. Extrapolation of these parameter values gives the dotted curves. Finally, with help of the numerical model based on the Brinkman equation and PGD, the permeability has been calculated as an average of values predicted over a series of cross-section image of Ud3.

Figure 4: Permeability values obtained for the three fabrics.

Experimental values of permeability show a clear enhancement between Ud1, Ud2 and Ud3, whatever the value of V_f is. The augmentation of weft yarns density between Ud1 and Ud2 improves saturated longitudinal permeability by between 2.2 and 4.7 for a range of V_f between 40% and 50% respectively. The increase of spacer yarns lineal weight by four between Ud2 and Ud3 induces doubling of permeability values for V_f between 43% and 53%. Modification of textile parameters changes macropores structure which, at a consequence, affects the fluid flow path and the permeability. All these conclusions about experimental values remain valid for KC2S model values. KC2S model permeability values for Ud2 compared to Ud1 and for Ud3 compared to Ud2 are about four times higher. These model ratios are not exactly the same as the experimental ones (between 2.2 and 4.7) but remain comparable.

KC2S model values are globally lower than experimental values. Brinkman/PGD predicted permeability value for Ud3 matches exactly with the corresponding KC2S curve. The work is in progress to get the Brinkman/PGD prediction of permeability values at other V_f to confirm this observation. In this case, the observed under-estimation of experimental permeability values is due to possible inaccuracies in the image processing, coming from the segmentation of different yarn regions. For instance, small pores between adjacent yarns may have been interpreted as regions belonging to yarns. A discussion is engaged in the following section about discrepancy between KC2S model and experiments.

4.2 Discussion about KC2S model

Experimental values of permeability are higher than KC2S model ones. Different explanations can be proposed and some of them are discussed here.

First, experimental values of permeability are difficult to determine with an absolute certainty. It is noticeable that no standard exists for permeability measurements actually. A few years ago, a benchmark study [4] over different permeability set-ups including ours showed differences of one order of magnitude maximum in permeability values for the same glass preform. Despite that, our set-up gave results among the lowest ones for the tested glass fabrics. This means that our actual experimental

values, measured in similar conditions compared to the benchmark, cannot be overestimated by much for practical reasons.

Then, KC2S model involves different parameters whose estimation or calculation can be discussed.

$A_A(P_M)$ corresponds to the fraction of area of porosity between the yarns divided by the whole surface of a cross-section image of the composite. To extract the macropores area from an image, some operations of image treatment like binarisation and filtering are needed. To ensure the validity of our method, these operations are made according to the same procedure for all images. Only a few characteristics used in the operations are changed to take into account images with more or less macropores. Relevance of macropores delimitation with original image in 256 grey levels is checked systematically at the end of image treatment. $A_A(P_M)$ is an important parameter as it is used with V_f to determine micropores areal fraction $A_A(P_\mu)$ also involved in the KC2S model.

Average radius of warp yarn fibers was given as $9.0\mu\text{m}$ and was checked for each fabric on cross-sections images. It gives r_f (Ud1) = $8.8\pm 0.76\mu\text{m}$, r_f (Ud2) = $9.05\pm 0.68\mu\text{m}$ and r_f (Ud3) = $9.02\pm 0.87\mu\text{m}$ for 413, 257 and 187 analyzed fibers respectively. All these measurements confirm the given value.

$\overline{L(P_M)}$ is averaged arithmetically over the values calculated in four directions. Arithmetic, geometric and harmonic averages were tested and gave very similar results.

The last parameter in KC2S model is an expression adapted from the Kozeny constant defined here by c_M and c_μ and used in Eq. 2. Different authors have debated about the possible values this constant may have, as already mentioned by Carman for different porous media [5]. More recent studies concerning fibrous media deal with variation of the Kozeny constant as a function of volume fraction of fibers. In our case, chosen values for both constants are $c_M = c_\mu = 0.9788$ calculated from the Gebart constant for hexagonal arrangement of fibers [6]. One can consider that micropores present an arrangement of fibers that results in a similar permeability to the hexagonal arrangement whereas macropores are organized in a very specific way. This means that $c_\mu = 0.9788$ is valid on one side and c_M takes different values on the other side. Reporting this assumption in the KC2S model (Eqs. 1 and 2) in order to achieve experimental values of permeability gives c_M values (Eq. 4) for the three preforms represented on Fig. 5.

$$c_M = 16 \frac{A_A(P)K_{exp} - K_\mu A_A(P_\mu)[1 - A_A(P_M)]}{A_A(P_M)^2 \overline{L(P_M)}^2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 5: c_M evolution obtained for the three fabrics at different porosity surface fraction.

Fig. 5 shows that the highest c_M is for Ud1 and the lowest one, for Ud3. All values are higher than 0.9788 obtained for a “regular” fibrous media. This could mean that, even if Ud3 experimental permeability is higher than Ud1 and Ud2 ones, permeability for Ud3 should have been higher if c_M had remained constant between Ud1 and Ud3. Changing textile parameters between Ud1 and Ud3 has led to a depreciation of c_M value.

This depreciation of c_M value may come from the fact that the KC2S model is calculated from cross-sections and doesn't take into account the evolution of the macropores structure along the warp direction as opposed to the real fabrics.

According to Eq. 2. and considering a single scale with $A_A(P_M) = A_A(P)$, c_M constant can be expressed in terms of the Kozeny constant k_K as follows (Eq. 5).

$$\frac{c_M \pi^2}{64} = \frac{1}{4k_K} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{with } k_K = K_0 K_1^2$$

Where K_0 and K_1 are parameters that define fabric structure morphology and tortuosity of its network [5].

Results shown in Fig. 5 are compared with the fitted values from Sullivan work on variation of Kozeny constant [7] as a function of macropores fraction area (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: k_K of the three fabrics compared to values from Sullivan work at different porosity surface fraction.

Fig. 6 shows that the evolution of Kozeny constant for Ud3 obtained from KC2S model remain comparable with Sullivan linear fitted values in a $A_A(P_M)$ range from 0.16 to 0.32.

5 RTM-TP: TECHNOLOGICAL FEASIBILITY

Once the longitudinal permeability has been enhanced, elaboration tests inside a dedicated mould are conducted with high fluidity 6,6 polyamide injected through Ud3 fabrics. Technical difficulties arise from: i. the high temperatures during moulding, i.e. around 300°C; ii. the deformation of the preform induced by the pressure exerted by the polymer flow; iii. the preferential channel flows at the edges of the preform. An operating point has been finally found after different trials with the parameters values given in Table 2.

Parameter	value	unity
Number of plies	7	-
Volume fraction of fibers	54.2	%
Thickness of the part	3.0	mm
Temperature of the injected polymer	300	°C
Average mould temperature	306	°C
Constant injection rate	5	cm ³ /min
Maximal pressure at the inlet	2.8	Bars
Injection length	400	mm

Table 2: Parameter values used in a successful RTM injection.

The corresponding composite plate injected at ~80% has been cut to obtain microstructure cross-sections along the injection length. It can be observed that the fabrics have remained in place during injection according to the vertical straight weft yarns (Fig. 7a) and that voids are only observed between both mould surfaces and the plies directly in contact with them (Fig. 7a). There is no visual difference between a cross-section at the inlet (A) and near the front (F) (Fig. 7b). This suggests that no compression of warp yarns occurs during the injection, i.e. that the pressure exerted on warp yarns by the flow of PA6,6 is lower than the compression of warp yarns due to the textile parameters.

Figure 7: Above view of the composite plate (a) and cross-section images along the length (b)

Nevertheless, injection time for this plate is estimated at around 32min and optimisation of the different parameters is still necessary to reduce significantly this amount of time.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Three types of a quasi-unidirectional fabric have been studied. Their structure remains the same and only one parameter is quantitatively changed each time one from one fabric type to another. Preforms with these three fabrics are elaborated and characterized in microstructure and longitudinal saturated permeability.

Experiments show the permeability increase with the increasing macropores content. A double-scale model based on Kozeny-Carman equation and a numerical model based on the Brinkman equation solved by the PGD and FEM are employed. These models seem to be consistent to each other, but show lower values than the experimental ones. This discrepancy may be assigned to the difference between 3D experiments and models applied to 2D images, as well as to the possible inaccuracies in the texture analysis during the image processing. Further developments can be improved at the stage of the texture analysis in image processing and by the employment of models in a 3D formulation and calculations over 3D images.

Double-scale KC2S model also shows that a slight modification in textile parameters affects permeability. The increased amount of macropores in the third fabric compared to the first one is noticeably limited in its influence on permeability by the different way the fluid flows through these macropores.

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